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Unveiling Glycan-Mediated Immune Responses in Congenital Disorders of Glycosylation and Cancer: Implications for Targeted Immunotherapies

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Understanding the intricacies of immune responses in relation to specific glycan modifications is crucial for advancing targeted immunotherapies. Our research focuses on elucidating how cell surface glycans influence immunity, with a particular emphasis on diseases characterized by altered glycosylation—congenital disorders of glycosylation (CDG) and cancer.

Congenital disorders of glycosylation (CDG), a group of approximately 170 rare genetic diseases, result from defects in glycosylation processes, often presenting with multi-systemic involvement. Immune complications significantly impact the quality of life for CDG patients, particularly those with PMM2-CDG, the most prevalent subtype. PMM2-CDG patients experience recurrent severe infections and exhibit adverse responses to inflammation. To decipher the immunological dysfunction in PMM2-CDG, we conducted comprehensive analyses of the transcriptome, signallome, and glycome in patients' cells following inflammatory stimuli. Our findings revealed decreased IL-6 cytokine expression, altered glycan profiles and dysregulation in the MAPK signaling pathway downstream of the TNF- α receptor in PMM2-CDG. Remarkably, GNE-CDG, a muscle disorder associated with sialic acid biosynthesis defects, also exhibited IL-6 expression defects, highlighting the major role of glycosylation in modulating the immune responses.

Our exploration of sialylated glycans extends to cancer research, with a specific focus on sialyl Tn (STn) aberrantly expressed in numerous cancers and linked to aggressiveness. STn impedes the maturation of immune cells, and it has been associated to several clinical features depending on the cancer types. Its cancer specificity prompted the development of novel antibodies with high specificity against STn and its derivatives. These antibodies exhibit intense reactivity to cancer tissues while sparing healthy tissues. Currently under investigation for therapeutic applications, these antibodies hold potential for advancing cancer immunotherapy.

This presentation will unveil our recent findings, shedding light on potential defects in biological pathways in CDG and cancer. Our research aims to identify novel biomarkers and contribute to the development of innovative therapies, furthering our understanding of the intricate interplay between glycan alterations and immune responses in these diverse pathological contexts.

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References:

1. Carrascal MA, ..., Videira PA. Sialyl Tn-expressing bladder cancer cells induce a tolerogenic phenotype in innate and adaptive immune cells. *Mol Oncol*. **2014**;8(3):753-65. doi: 10.1016/j.molonc.2014.02.008.
 2. Loureiro LR, ..., Palma AS, Novo C, Videira PA. Novel monoclonal antibody L2A5 specifically targeting sialyl-Tn and short glycans terminated by alpha-2-6 sialic acids. *Sci Rep*. **2018**;8(1):12196. doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-30421-w.
- Francisco R, Pascoal C, ... Dos Reis Ferreira V, Videira PA. New Insights into Immunological Involvement in Congenital Disorders of Glycosylation (CDG) from a People-Centric Approach. *J Clin Med*. **2020**; 9:2092. doi: 10.3390/jcm9072092.